

**RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN STUDY HABITS AND ACADEMIC
ACHIEVEMENT OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENT**

Education

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the degree of relationship between study habits and academic achievement of 10th grade students. The study employed a descriptive research of survey type. ASHI (Study Habit Inventory) was employed to determine the study habits of students. An academic achievement test was also developed to measure the achievement of the students in terms of scores. A reliability coefficient of 0.91 was obtained using split half method. The population of the study includes all the secondary school students of Karnal city. Sample were selected through purpose random sampling technique. The Hypothesis was tested using Persons Correlation. The findings of this study habits would be of immense help in improving the study habits of the students at secondary level. Improvement in students academic achievements will further had to national development as competent manpower will be produced planning of specific items for study is highly recommended.

Introduction

Many students fail not because they lack ability, but because they do not have adequate Study skills (Menzel, 1982). Study habit is the tendency of a student to learn in a systematic and efficient way when opportunity is given. Good students are not seen but are made by Constant and deliberate practice of good study habits, for which there is no substitute (Ames & Archer, 1988). Development of good study habits in children depends upon the combined efforts of parents and teachers (Kizlik, 2001).

The development of good study habits is the highway to the goals of an individual, whatever, they are. A sample, small change in study habits makes a big difference in goal setting and organization of one's life. The success of an individual depends upon his study habits.

Good study habits lead to good academic record and bad study habits lead to poor academic record as there is direct relationship between study habits and academic achievement. Study habits play an important role in human performance in academic field (Verma, 1996, Verma & Kumar 1999; Satapathy & Singhal, 2000) Gorrism (1980), Cuff (1980) stated that training in study habits increases academic achievement. Gupta Asha (1990) stated that there exists a positive correlation between study habits and academic achievement. Susan Jacob (2002) founded correlation between achievement motivation and academic achievement.

Accepting study habit is an important factor in learning, it is necessary to investigate into nature and also to know whether it is related to factors like personality, intelligence, academic achievement etc.

Need of the study

In order to improve the quality of education we must develop certain innovative strategies which will enhance the educational standards. In addition to the student's side there must be some important steps, which form the bases of their academic achievement. Student need requirements, abilities, capabilities, their pattern of studying etc. have been neglected for a long time and they were forced to learn the same thing, by the same method, by the same persons in the same environment. Efficient learning depends upon the development of good reading habits.

As the societies have come under the impact of science and technology there are many means and many sources of learning. The teacher should be aware of the various laws and theories of learning and their educational applications. It is not only the teacher's responsibility to provide learning experiences, but it is also the responsibility of the pupils to utilize their property by adopting efficient procedure of learning or by developing proper study habits during teaching and learning procedures from mobile.

Successful achievement in any form of activity is based upon study, interpretation and application (Yologe 1990); and that study should have a purpose. Isangedighi (1997) reports strong correlation between study habits and academic achievement of high school students. According to (Fagbemi, 2001) the degree of learning depends on the amount of time the child is actively engaged in learning. The time spent on studying helps students to retain the material learnt, which will eventually boost the students performance outcome during tests or examinations therefore, this study investigates the relationship between secondary school student's study habit and their academic achievement. Keeping in mind, the purpose of study was to find the relationship between study habits and achievement of secondary school students. The study believed that if student's study habits are improved and made consistent, academic performance would definitely improve. The knowledge of student's degree of study would of course help the teachers and counselors to select appropriate techniques of helping students.

Review of Related Literature

Individual study habits play a private role in determining in a pupil's academic achievement. A student's progress or failure in the classroom depends upon several factors, namely interest in the subject, study facilities, own study habits and so on.

Carter (1950) conducted two study method tests on 800 educational psychology students. He compared the study habits score with the composite measure of achievement. The correlation ranged from 0.46 to 0.51. Mortun (1959) made an investigation on the relationship of study habits and achievement in IX grade general sciences. He found that achievement in IX grade general sciences was not associated with study habits. Patel (1981) and Chauhan and Singh (1982) found that a positive relationship between study habits and academic achievement of school going children. Dels and Grewal (1990) revealed that after their investigation on B. Sc final year Home Science students; the component of study habits are positively correlated with the academic

performance of students ($r=0.39$). Students with good study habits do better academically. Therefore, parents and teachers should help to promote good study habits in their children right from the beginning. Chopra (1996) identified that the study habits were positively related to academic achievement. Verma (1996) showed that students possessing good study habits scored higher achievements than students possessing poor study habits in the English, Hindi and Social Studies. On the other hand, students having poor and good study habits scored almost equal achievement in Mathematical & General Science. Nuthane & Yenage (2009) has examined the causes of poor academic performance among university undergraduates. Some of these factors identified are intellectual ability, poor study habits, achievement motivation, lack of vocational goals, self concept, low socio- economic status of the family, poor family structure and so on.

Chand (2013) has examined that by applying the components of study habits in learning process, students can increase their achievement.

The above studies on study habits and academic achievement have shown that they are both relevant variables, which influence the quality and quantity of work output. Academic achievement can be improved by creating good study habits which students can stimulate towards study.

Purpose of the study

The investigator has sought to examine the relationship between study habits and academic achievement of senior secondary school students. The investigator, on the basis of his finding also aimed at providing few tips and suggestions in order to excel the academic performance of the learner.

Statement of the Study

Relationship between Study Habits and Academic Achievement of Secondary School Students

Operational Definition of the Key Terms

Study Habits are defined as “the sum of all the habits determined, purposes and enforced practices that the individual uses in order to learn (Rao Study Inventory manual). Here the investigator means the same.

➤ **Academic Achievement :**

Academic Achievement means the marks scored in a test.

➤ **Secondary School Students**

By Secondary School Students means the students studying in the class IX.

Objectives of the study Hypothesis

To find out the Relationship between Study Habits and Academic Achievement of Secondary

School Students

Delimitations of the study

The present study was confined to:

1. 100 students of class IX of Karnal city.
2. Mathematics subject

3. Sub topics: Lateral/Curved Surface Area, Total Surface Areas, Volumes of different geometrical figures as Cuboids, Cube, Right Circular Cylinder, Right Circular Cone, and Sphere under the main topic "Surface areas and Volumes".

Hypothesis :- There is relationship between Study habits and Academic Achievement of senior secondary school students

Method of the study

The study employed a descriptive research of survey design. The population consisted of all senior secondary school students of Karnal city . Sample of 100 senior secondary school students studying in class IX were selected using purposive random sampling technique from the 3 senior secondary schools of Karnal city.

A study habit inventory developed by Mukhopadlya, M and Sansanal D.N (1985) was used to measure the study habits of the students at the secondary level was used. For the present inventory, the study habits have been considered to be constituted to nine different kinds of study behaviors. These are: Comprehension (12 items), Concentration (10 items), Task Orientation, study size (7 items), Interaction (3 items), Drilling (4 items), Supports (4 items), Recordings (2 items) and language (1 item). There were 52 items on five point scale (always, frequently, sometimes, the items have been drafted in affirmative (34 items) and negative (18 items) rarely and never). The reliability of the inventory on the basis of split half method was 0.89 and test retest method 0.92.

An Achievement Test was planned with the objective of measuring Achievement in Mathematics of IX grade students on selected topics. For the planning of Achievement Test following points were taken into accounts;

- Determining the purpose of a test;
- Identification and defining the intended learning outcomes;
- Preparing the test specifications; and
- Constructing relevant test items;

So, the Achievement Test having 80 objective type items was planned in mathematics of 1X class students on topic **Surface Areas and Volumes**

Results

Hypothesis: - There is relationship between academic achievement and study habits of senior secondary school students.

Table: Coefficient of correlation ‘r’ between Study habits and academic achievement

Coefficient of correlation in between ‘r’ Study habits and academic achievement	r =.90
	High and Positive Correaltion

This table revealed that the correlation coefficient between study habits and academic achievement is 0.90. This shows positive high correlation between academic achievement and study habits . It means that when there is an increase in the scores of study habits there will be also an increase in the academic achievements of the students. Thus, this hypothesis is accepted.

Conclusion

From the analysis it was found that there is significant relationship between study habits and academic achievement of senior secondary school students. Thus, it is clear that the study habit has an impact on the academic achievement

Recommendations:

The present study findings on study habits correlates with previous research that found that students who invest more in school do better" (Battle and Lewis, 2002) and that those who exude more effort also perform better (Carbonaro, 2005 cited by Barry, 2006). Therefore, the teachers and parents should identify good study habits and find ways and means of enhancing them among students.

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